

WAYS TO IMPROVE THE ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISM OF USING FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE SERVICE SECTOR

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Annotation: Provides a way to improve the organizational and economic mechanism of Health Systems, solve health problems, provide services to more people, use new technologies and coordinate not only organizational and economic, but also social issues. This article provides brief definitions and advice on ways to improve the organizational and economic mechanism of service delivery in the health care system.

Keywords: resource, planning, provider, telemedicine, household services, service network, efficiency, digital economy, information technology, digitization, customer orientation, innovation, quality of service, costs.

INTRODUCTION. In the world, the deepening of the globalization process and the fight against antimonopoly policies, the sharpening of competition, the priority of quality indicators in increasing the level of production and provision of services, the socio-economic importance of their sector is growing. In particular, the objective need for the development of domestic services is explained by the fact that it increases the quality of living standards of the population, as well as its positive effect on the increase in the level of employment.

"The share of the services sector of the developed countries of the world in gross domestic product is 75 percent, and the employment balance is more than 70 percent. If we analyze employment in the sectors and sectors of the economy in terms of services, it has increased by 75% in European countries, 80% in the United States, and 82% in Japan". It is for this reason that special

attention is paid to the development of the world's services sector, the development of modern types of services, increasing the volume and quality of services

REVIEW OF THEMATIC LITERATURE. Scientific, theoretical, methodological foundations of the development of the field of service, in particular, domestic service within the framework of research work M.Y.Porter, B.S.Santo, CA.X.Huxever, R.S.Russell, R.G.Merdick, A.P.Chelenkov, V.V.Kulibanova, S.N.Korobkova, V.I.Kravchenko, I.P.While studied by Pavlova et al, one of the scholars from Uzbekistan is YO.A.Abdullayev, Q.J.Mirzayev, M.M.Mukhammedov, B.A.Abdukarimov, M.Q.Pardayev, I.S.Tukhliyev, J.R.Zainalov, N.Tokhliyev, I.Ivatov, K.B.Urazov, Sh.S.Sharifov, E.S.Faiziyev, B. SH.Safarov, M.T.Alimova, U.R.It is reflected in the scientific research work of the likes of Matyakubov.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY. Methods such as systematic analysis, logic, induction and deduction, analysis and synthesis, comparative analysis were used when writing a scientific article. Also, for analysis, from statistics on the types of services of the Republic of Uzbekistan, legal and regulatory documents on the service sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan are also studied.

ANALYZES AND MAIN RESULTS. As one of the important factors and directions of deepening, digitization, employment, poverty reduction, improving the income and quality of life of the population in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the rapid development of the service and service sector remains one of the priority issues. The service sector covers the reproduction of types of services to consumers, each of which is suitable for specific types of activities.

The health system plays a decisive role in society by providing essential services to improve the well-being and quality of life of people. However, in many countries, the organizational and economic mechanisms of support for health services are often subject to many problems. These challenges range from inefficiencies in resource allocation to the inadequacy of financial models, and ultimately affect the availability, quality, and affordability of Health Services. To solve these problems, it is necessary to focus on improving the organizational and economic mechanisms in the health system. This article explores various strategies and approaches to improve health care delivery, to ensure a more efficient and efficient system.

Table 1.

Changes in the total volume of services and household services provided to the population in Uzbekistan in 2018-2022

Specification	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2022 change from 2018	
						+/-	%
Total services provided in Uzbekistan, billion. Soum	11113,6 1	14058,8	19292,0	26455,8	31785,8	20672,2	286,0
Domestic services in Uzbekistan, billion. Soum	187,1	253,9	326,9	430,7	551,4	364,3	294,7
Share of household services in total services in Uzbekistan, %	1,68	1,81	1,69	1,63	1,73	+0,05	X

From analyzes, it can be seen that the volume of household services has increased from year to year, and this was also greatly influenced by the cost of household services provided mainly. It is known that in recent years, the cost of household services has increased 20-22 times depending on the types of services provided.

Especially in the last 4-5 years, this increase was noticeable. Unlike goods, services cannot take the form of a material object. Service and their production are inseparable and complementary components from each other. Services represent the results of various activities carried out by manufacturers on consumer orders, and usually lead to a change in the state of units.

The changes that consumers expect in service will depend on:

A. To carry out certain operations with the goods belonging to the consumer producing the service, that is, such as their transportation, cleaning, repair;

B. The service provider provides therapeutic or surgical assistance to people, changes their appearance, provides educational, informative and consulting services, organizes entertainment programs;

C. The manufacturer provides insurance, financial intermediary services, provides protection, provides bail.

Changes like these can be temporary or permanent in nature. As a result of the provision of services in the field of healthcare, medical services or education, long-term changes in the state of consumers can occur, and the advantage of these changes can be used for many years. A group of industries is usually classified as a service sector, even if they are engaged in the production of a product with many characteristics of the goods. This group includes the creation of informative programs, the preparation of materials with a news and Advice feature, the development of software, the creation of Motion Pictures and music programs, among others.

It should be noted that at present, the following organizational and economic problems are an obstacle to the development of the services sector and its effectiveness in our republic:

- ✓ lack of demand for the modernization and diversification of the services sector;
- ✓ the failure to establish specific innovative directions for the development and efficiency of the services sector and market;
- ✓ insufficient consideration of the effects of various external factors (natural disasters, disease and pandemic consequences) in the development of the services sector in the regions;
- ✓ the incomplete development of the organizational and economic mechanism in accordance with the requirements of the digital economy in the processes and measures of the development of the services sector;
- ✓ insufficient use of world experience in the development of the services sector, especially in the Republic and its territories of advanced achievements in industrially developed foreign countries;
- ✓ low application of innovation in the development of the services sector, especially in the case of future services, failure to establish systematic work on innovation-based services.

Table 2.

Growth rates of the main indicators of the service sector in Uzbekistan

Specification name	Years					2022-2018 relatively, in %
	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	
Share of the service sector in the country's GDP,%	39,9	38,1	35,9	35,5	36,3	92

Total rendered services volume, trln.Soum	97,1	118,8	150,9	193,7	218,9	225,4
The volume of services per capita, million.Soum	3.0	3,7	4,6	5,8	6,4	213

Effective and efficient medical services are crucial to the welfare and development of societies. One of the main aspects of improving the health care system is the efficient allocation of resources. Health organizations must strategically distribute their resources, including personnel, medical equipment, and equipment, to ensure optimal use. To achieve this, the following measures can be considered:

A. Comprehensive planning: developing a comprehensive plan that assesses the existing health infrastructure, population needs, and disease burden will help identify gaps in resources and effectively manage resource allocation decisions.

B. Data-based approaches: data analysis and the use of advanced technology can provide valuable information about patient demographics, disease patterns, and resource utilization, allowing healthcare providers to allocate resources based on evidence-based decision-making.

C. Collaboration and coordination: promoting collaboration and coordination between health providers and stakeholders helps to share resources, reduce repeatability, and optimize resource utilization.

It is very important to invest in robust primary care services for the overall improvement of the health care system. By prioritizing prevention, early diagnosis and treatment of chronic diseases in the primary stage, the burden of secondary and tertiary medical facilities can be reduced. The following measures can be taken to strengthen primary care:

❖ Infrastructure development: providing appropriate infrastructure and equipment in primary care centers can improve the ability of the population to receive timely medical care.

❖ Education and training: providing continuing education and training to primary care providers can increase their skills in diagnostic, therapeutic and preventive care, reducing the need for special services.

❖ Technology integration: integration of Digital Health Solutions and telemedicine platforms into the primary care system will improve access to remote areas and enable timely consultation, diagnosis and subsequent medical care.

The economic mechanism of Health Services plays a decisive role in ensuring financial stability at low cost for patients. The implementation of effective financial models will help to solve existing problems and more effectively develop the health system. The following strategies can be considered:

I. Health insurance reform: a review of health insurance policies to ensure comprehensive coverage including prevention, outpatient services, and catastrophic events can minimize financial burdens on individuals and ensure fair access to health services.

II. Payment reform: the transition from pay-for-service models to value-based payment systems may encourage medical service providers to focus on quality service delivery, patient outcomes, and cost-effectiveness rather than the volume of services provided.

Public-Private Partnership: a partnership between the public and private sectors helps to use resources, expertise and innovation to improve health care delivery. Such cooperation will help the health sector to compete, efficiency and invest. Technological advances have the potential to revolutionize the provision of Health Services. Integration of innovative technologies can simplify

processes, improve patient experience, and improve health outcomes. The following areas are important:

✓ Electronic health records (EHR): the introduction of powerful EHR systems ensures safe and efficient data exchange, improves medical care coordination, reduces medical errors, and enables data-based decision-making.

✓ Telemedicine and remote monitoring: the expansion of telemedicine services and remote monitoring technologies can improve the use of medical services, especially for rural and low-income populations. This allows for remote consultations, home care and timely measures.

✓ Artificial intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML): AI and ML algorithms can analyze large amounts of medical data, assist in diagnosis, predict and predict disease progression.

Important ways to improve the organizational and economic mechanism of service provision in the health system are improving legal management, effectively using financial resources, training and motivating employees, studying and using large information technologies, improving guarantees, applying and mastering innovations, establishing cooperation with public organizations and internal and external institutions. These techniques help improve the quality, effectiveness, and performance of services in the health care system, and make it possible to ensure that the community achieves health care.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS. Optimally taking into account the modernization and diversification of the service sector, the implementation of changes in its composition in accordance with the requirements of the Times, boorish remains an important factor in increasing the volume of added value in GDP. The share of the service sector in the economy of our republic is growing significantly.

Such an increase in the service sector is influenced by several factors, including the emergence of the need of people in the market for new services, for example, in the conditions of a digital economy, making payments through credit cards without going to the bank, internets hoping, the opening of modern shopping centers, catering enterprises, hotels, the expansion of educational services, recreational art, tourism.

Services as a special commodity require its market to be valid under special conditions. In particular, the market for household services, according to its characteristics, differs from each other in cities and villages.

These differences are the features of the organization of household services, the level of development of the infrastructure of services, the level of income of the population, depends on the S. Further development of information supply in the field of household services provides an opportunity to more fully satisfy the population's need for household services, assess the dynamics of growth in this area and improve the quality and efficiency of the services provided.

To do this, it is necessary to establish special services – marketing Centers for the study of the demand for household services on a territorial scale.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE

1. Саттарова З. И. Проблемы развития культурного туризма в Самаркандской области //Молодой ученый. – 2018. – №. 21. – С. 300-303.
2. Саттарова З. И. Возможности создания туристского кластера в Самаркандской области //Молодой ученый. – 2019. – №. 22. – С. 586-588.
3. Асланова Д. Х., Саттарова З. И., Алимова М. Т. Региональный туристский кластер как инструмент повышения эффективности экономики региона //Научный результат. Экономические исследования. – 2016. – Т. 2. – №. 1 (7). – С. 18-25.

4. Uzakova V. et al. Transportation system in the development of Uzbekistan //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2016. – Т. 6. – №. 1. – С. 120-134.
5. Aslanov D. H., Sattarova Z. I., Alimova M. T. Regional tourist cluster as a tool of increase of efficiency of economy of region //Scientific results. Economic studies. – 2016. – Т. 2. – С. 18.
6. Sattarova Z. I. THE EUROPEAN EXPERIENCE OF ORGANIZING RURAL TOURISM IN THE CONTEXT OF A PANDEMIC //Gospodarka i Innowacje. – 2022. – Т. 23. – С. 605-607.
7. Шадиева Г. М., Саттарова З. И. ПРОБЛЕМЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ТУРИСТСКИХ КЛАСТЕРОВ В САМАРКАНДСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ //ЭКОНОМИКА В МЕНЯЮЩЕМСЯ МИРЕ. – 2022. – С. 439.
8. Шадиева Г. М., Саттарова З. И. ПРОБЛЕМЫ РАЗВИТИЯ КУЛЬТУРНОГО ТУРИЗМА В САМАРКАНДСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ //ЭКОНОМИКА В МЕНЯЮЩЕМСЯ МИРЕ. – 2022. – С. 442.
9. Саттарова З. И. Опыт зарубежных стран в развитии региональных туристских кластеров Узбекистана //Молодой ученый. – 2019. – №. 23. – С. 307-309.
10. Aslanova D. K., Sattarova Z. I., Alimova M. T. Regional tourist cluster as a tool to improve the efficiency of the region's economy. Scientific result //Economic Research. – 2016. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 7.
11. Aslanova D. H., Sattarova Z. I., Alimova M. T. Regional'nyj turistskij klaster kak instrument povysheniya jeffektivnosti jekonomiki regiona //Nauchnyj rezul'tat. Jekonomicheskie issledovaniya, 2. – 2016. – №. 1 (7)).
12. Ilkhamovna S. Z., Javohir F., Ulugbekovich K. D. Development of Tourism Clusters in the Samarkand Region //Nexus: Journal of Advances Studies of Engineering Science. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 160-166.
13. Ilkhamovna S. Z., Diyora G., Ulugbekovich K. D. Development of Culture Tourism in the Samarkand Region //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BUSINESS DIPLOMACY AND ECONOMY. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 152-158.
14. Baxtiyorovna M. G., Abdukhalilovich S. S., Nodirovna M. S. Directions of Improvement of the Mechanism of State Support of Business Entities //Pioneer: Journal of Advanced Research and Scientific Progress. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 1-7.
15. Ilkhamovna S. Z., Zuvaydullo X. Strategy For the Development of Regional Cultural Tourism in Central Asian Countries (On the Great Silk Road) //Gospodarka i Innowacje. – 2023. – Т. 35. – С. 590-599.
16. Ilkhamovna S. Z., Nodir B. Foreign Experience of Legal Regulation of Agro Ecotourism //Journal of Intellectual Property and Human Rights. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 178-184.
17. Sattarova Z. I. et al. Problems of Cultural Tourism Development and Trends of Its Development in the City of Samarkand //International Journal on Integrated Education. – 2022. – Т. 5. – №. 5. – С. 303-310.
18. Саттарова З. И. Приоритетные направления формирования регионального туристского кластера //Молодой ученый. – 2019. – №. 23. – С. 304-307.
19. Boliboev A. A. et al. METHODS OF PLANNING PRODUCTION PROCESSES //GospodarkaiInnowacje. – 2022. – Т. 24. – С. 961-964.

20. Yazdonov Q. G., Ubaydullayev B. S., Mirzaeva S. N. THE PROBLEM OF ORGANIZING THE WORKPLACE AT THE ENTERPRISE //GospodarkaiInnowacje. – 2022. – T. 24. – C. 982-985.
21. Djaborovna P. D. et al. Opportunities for Small Business and Private Entrepreneurship Development in Rural Areas //American Journal of Economics and Business Management. – 2022. – T. 5. – №. 6. – C. 141-145.
22. Uktamova D. B., Ubaydullayev B. S., Mirzaeva S. N. Factors of Improving the Organization of Labor at the Enterprise //Kresna Social Science and Humanities Research. – 2022. – T. 5. – C. 88-91.
23. Nortojev M. A., Ubaydullayev B. S., Mirzaeva S. N. On the Issue of Certification of Workplaces According to Working Conditions //Kresna Social Science and Humanities Research. – 2022. – T. 5. – C. 94-96.
24. Hamitov S. I., Ubaydullayev B. S., Mirzaeva S. N. Organization of Staff Work at the Enterprise //Kresna Social Science and Humanities Research. – 2022. – T. 5. – C. 97-100.
25. Nodirovna M. S., Faxriddinovich U. F., Dusmurotovich U. M. Ways and Prospects for Developing the System of Residential Services in Rural Areas, Increasing Employment //Academic Journal of Digital Economics and Stability. – 2022. – T. 17. – C. 96-101.
26. Nodirovna M. S., Ugli S. T. T., Abduazizovich A. I. WAYS TO INCREASE THE EFFICIENCY OF GOVERNMENT SERVICES IN THE EMPLOYMENT OF THE POPULATION IN UZBEKISTAN //GospodarkaiInnowacje. – 2022. – T. 23. – C. 29-37.
27. Nodirovna M. S., Mamasoliyevna K. C., Ugli S. J. U. The composition of the income of service workers and ways of its improvement (on the example of educational institutions) //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 12. – №. 4. – C. 213-218.
28. Zugurova Z. D., Ubaydullayev B. S. and Mirzaeva S. N. (2022). EFFICIENT PLANNING OF PRODUCTION PROCESSES. International Conference on Research Identity, Value and Ethics, [online] pp.416–418.
29. Yakhyoyeva S. O., Ubaydullayev B. S. and Mirzaeva S. N. (2022). FEATURES OF THE DIVISION AND COOPERATION OF LABOR AT THE ENTERPRISE. International Conference on Research Identity, Value and Ethics, [online] pp.413–415.
30. Mamayunusovich, P. O., & Nodirovna, M. S. (2022). Management of the Mechanism of Storage and Sale of Products in the Republic of Uzbekistan. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF BUSINESS STARTUPS AND OPEN SOCIETY, 2(5), 67–71.
31. Saidakhmedovich, S. T. ., Nodirovna, M. S. ., &Khaydarjanovna, S. D. . (2022). Ways to Improve the Performance of Service Enterprises in Rural Areas. Middle European Scientific Bulletin, 24, 21-24.
32. M.S.Nodirovna, Shaptakov and Mamasoliyevna, K.C. (2022). Improving the Economic Impact of Increasing Foreign Investment in Uzbekistan in the Digital Economic Environment. AcademicJournalofDigitalEconomicsandStability, [online] 16, pp.160–165
33. M.S. Nodirovna, Ta’nakulovich, T.K. and Baxtiyorovich, S.J. (2022). WAYS TO IMPROVE THE EFFICIENCY OF MEDICAL SERVICES IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY. GospodarkaiInnowacje., [online] 22, pp.182–186.
34. МирзаеваШиринНодировна (2022). ЎЗБЕКИСТОНШАРОИТИДААҲОЛИНИИШБИЛАНТАЪМИНЛАШСОҲАСИДАДАВЛАТ ХИЗМАТЛАРИСАМАРАДОРЛИГИНИОШИРИШЎЛЛАРИ.БАРҚАРОРЛИКВАЕТАКЧИТ АДҚИҚОТЛАРОНЛАЙНИЛМИЙЖУРНАЛИ, [online] 2(4), pp.428–438.

35. M.S.Nodirovna, S.T.Ugli., and A.I. Abduazizovich, (2022). WAYS TO INCREASE THE EFFICIENCY OF GOVERNMENT SERVICES IN THE EMPLOYMENT OF THE POPULATION IN UZBEKISTAN. *Gospodarka i Innowacje*, [online] 23, pp.29–37.
36. Nodirovna, M.S., Bakhtiyorovich, S.J. and Ta'nakulovich, T.K. (2022). Prospects for the Development of Small Business and Entrepreneurship in the Digital Economy. *American Journal of Economics and Business Management*, [online] 5(3), pp.248–252.
37. Mirzaeva, S. Nodirovna (2022). Ways to Increase Investment Potential in Samarkand Region. *International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding*, 9(2), p.471. doi:10.18415/ijmmu.v9i2.3542.
38. Sidorov V. A. et al. INNOVATSIYA IQTISODIYOTI: TEXNOLOGIK YUTUQ MUAMMOSI //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2023. – T. 3. – №. 2. – С. 8-15.
39. Saidakhmedovich S. T., Bekhruz U. PROBLEMS OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS IN THE REAL SECTOR //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 10. – №. 10. – С. 624-628.
40. Шарипов Т. С. Важность организации ресторанных услуг в управлении гостиничным бизнесом //Молодой ученый. – 2020.
41. Sharipov T. Овқатланиш хизматлари бозорида рақобатбардошлик масалалари //Iqtisodiyot va innovatsion texnologiyalar. – 2017. – №. 1. – С. 136-142.
42. Nodirovna M. S. ESTABLISHMENT AND MAINTENANCE OF CENTRALIZED SERVICE AGENCIES IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN //Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities. – 2023. – Т. 11. – №. 1. – С. 631-637.
43. Nodirovna M. S., Ugli S. T. T., Abduazizovich A. I. WAYS TO INCREASE THE EFFICIENCY OF GOVERNMENT SERVICES IN THE EMPLOYMENT OF THE POPULATION IN UZBEKISTAN //Gospodarka i Innowacje. – 2022. – Т. 23. – С. 29-37.
44. Artikov Z. S. In Competitions Conductrd by Belt Wrestling Use of Fast Technical Methods Efficiency //American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 11. – С. 253-255.
45. Saifiddinovich A. Z., Shokhrukhovich U. F. Social Protection of the Unemployed and their Labor Increasing Competitiveness in the Market //American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 3. – С. 61-63.
46. Артиков З. С. ЯНГИ ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА РАҚАМЛИ ИҚТИСОДИЁТНИНГ НАЗАРИЙ АСОСЛАРИ //Экономика и финансы (Узбекистан). – 2022. – №. 4 (152). – С. 59-65.
47. Uralovich A. N., Abdulloevich N. D., Sayfiddinovich A. Z. An Analysis of the Demographic Data of Population of the Republic of Uzbekistan //American journal of social and humanitarian research. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 10. – С. 15-22.
48. Nodirovna, M. S. ., Feruz, E. ., Rustambek, K. ., & Khudoyor, A. . (2023). Ways of Attracting Investments in Service Enterprises of the Republic of Uzbekistan. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BUSINESS DIPLOMACY AND ECONOMY*, 2(3), 81–87. Retrieved from <http://inter-publishing.com/index.php/ijbde/article/view/1269>
49. Abdurkarimov F. B. RESEARCH AND SYSTEMATIZATION OF TRADE SERVICES SERVES TO IMPROVE THE COUNTRY'S ECONOMY IN THE CORONAVIRUS PANDEMY PERIOD //Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 1.1 Economical sciences.

50. Абдукаримов Ф. Б. Савдода бозор механизмини такомиллаштириш ва самарадорлигини ошириш йўллари (Самарқанд вилояти мисолида) //Иқтисодиёт фанлари номзоди илмий даражасини олиш учун ёзилган диссертация. Самарқанд: СамИСИ. – 2011. – Т. 156.
51. Мирзаева Ш. Н. и др. ЎЗБЕКИСТОН ШАРОИТИДА АҲОЛИНИ ИШ БИЛАН ТАЪМИНЛАШ СОҲАСИДА ДАВЛАТ ХИЗМАТЛАРИ САМАРАДОРЛИГИНИ ОШИРИШ ЙЎЛЛАРИ //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 428-438.
52. Anvar, K. . (2023). The Current State of the Industry and Service Sector of Sports Tourism of Uzbekistan. *World of Science: Journal on Modern Research Methodologies*, 2(4), 12–17. Retrieved from <http://univerpubl.com/index.php/woscience/article/view/880>
53. Anvar, K. . (2023). Foreign Experience in the Development of Sports Tourism. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BUSINESS DIPLOMACY AND ECONOMY*, 2(4), 1–10. Retrieved from <http://inter-publishing.com/index.php/ijbde/article/view/1366>
54. Sultanovich M. D., Zuvaydullo X., Ulugbekovich K. D. Improvement of Organizational and Economic Mechanisms of Economic Growth in the Service Sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BUSINESS DIPLOMACY AND ECONOMY. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 126-133.
55. Musinov Dilshod Sultanovich, Erdonov Mukhammadamin Erdon o‘g‘li, & Ibragimov Azamat Sobir o‘g‘li. (2023). APPLICATION OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN A MARKET ECONOMY. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 8(2), 23–26. Retrieved from <http://web-journal.ru/index.php/journal/article/view/1012>
56. Sultanovich M. D. Opportunities to Create New Jobs Through the Development of the Service Sector //Nexus: Journal of Advances Studies of Engineering Science. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 113-122.
57. Мусинов Д. ХИЗМАТ КЎРСАТИШ СОҲАСИНИНИНГИЖТИМОЙ ВА ИҚТИСОДИЙ САМАРАДОРЛИГИИҚТИСОДИЙ ЎСИШ ОМИЛИ СИФАТИДА //Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 12/1.
58. Sultanovich M. D., Ug‘li N. S. S. Opportunities to Ensure the Stability of the National Banking System and Apply Foreign Experience to Uzbekistan //Gospodarka i Innowacje. – 2024. – Т. 43. – С. 85-94.
59. Sultanovich M. D. IMPROVEMENT OF ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS OF ECONOMIC GROWTH IN THE SERVICE FIELD //Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities. – 2023. – Т. 11. – №. 1. – С. 619-630.
60. Sultanovich M. D. THE MAIN DIRECTIONS OF POVERTY REDUCTION IN OUR COUNTRY //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2023. – Т. 11. – №. 2. – С. 164-171.
61. Sultanovich M. D. IMPROVING THE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN THE CONTEXT OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY //Journal of Modern Educational Achievements. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 3. – С. 51-58.
62. Pulatov M. E. On the Need And Ways of Converting Some of the Components of Goodwill Into Identifiable Intangible Assets //Indonesian Journal of Innovation Studies. – 2019. – Т. 8.

63. Pulatov M. E. Conceptual Issues Of Accounting Of Intellectual Capital //American Journal of Economics and Business Management. – 2019. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 117-123.
64. Pulatov M. System Analysis Of Intellectual Property Indicators Of Financial Statements //European Journal of Business and Economics. – 2012. – Т. 6.
65. Pulatov M. INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY PARAMETERS OF FINANCIAL REPORTING. – 2016.
66. Nodirovna M. S. O'ZBEKISTONDA AXBOROT-TEXNOLOGIYALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING IQTISODIY-HUQUQIY ASOSLARI //The Role of Technical Sciences in IV Industrial Civilization: International Scientific and Practical Conference (UK). – 2023. – Т. 4. – С. 153-164.
67. NODIROVNA M. S. ON THE CREATION OF ADDITIONAL PRODUCTS IN THE SERVICE PROCESS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN //ТА'ЛИМ ВА INNOVATSION TADQIQOTLAR. – 2023. – Т. 11. – С. 76-85.
68. Мирзаева Ш. Н., Мухидинов Д. Д. МИФЫ ЭКОНОМИКИ //Gospodarka i Innowacje. – 2023. – Т. 41. – С. 283-287.
69. NODIROVNA M. S. BANKING SERVICES IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. – 2023.
70. Nodirovna M. S. NOVELTY OF BANKING SERVICES IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN //The Journal of Economics, Finance and Innovation. – 2023. – С. 620-628.
71. Nodirovna M. S. Management of Service Processes in Service Enterprises in the Republic of Uzbekistan //Formation and Development of Pedagogical Creativity: International Scientific-Practical Conference (Belgium). – 2023. – Т. 2. – С. 32-41.
72. Nodirovna M. S. The Current State of Activity and State Policy in the Field of Economic Development of Service Sector Entities in the Republic of Uzbekistan //Nexus: Journal of Advances Studies of Engineering Science. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 218-226.
73. Курбанова Р., Мирзаева Ш. РОЛЬ ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОГО КАПИТАЛА В СТИМУЛИРОВАНИИ ИННОВАЦИОННОГО РАЗВИТИЯ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ //Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 12/1.
74. Nodirovna M. S., Ugli S. T. T., Abduazizovich A. I. WAYS TO INCREASE THE EFFICIENCY OF GOVERNMENT SERVICES IN THE EMPLOYMENT OF THE POPULATION IN UZBEKISTAN //Gospodarka i Innowacje. – 2022. – Т. 23. – С. 29-37.
75. Nodirovna M. S. FINANCING OF INVESTMENT ACTIVITIES IMPORTANCE OF SOURCES //Section A-Research paper Article History: Received. – 2022. – Т. 12.
76. Nodirovna M. S. Banks and Development of Banking Services in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education, 2 (6), 21–30. – 1910.
77. Nodirovna M. S. Foreign Experience in Supporting Entrepreneurship and Business Activity of Women. WEB OF SYNERGY: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal Volume2, Issue 5Year2023ISSN: 2835-3013<https://univerpubl.com/index.php/synergy> <https://scholar.google.com/citations>.
78. Nodirovna M. S., Ugli S. T. T. and AI Abduazizovich,(2022). WAYS TO INCREASE THE EFFICIENCY OF GOVERNMENT SERVICES IN THE EMPLOYMENT OF THE POPULATION IN UZBEKISTAN //Gospodarka i Innowacje. – С. 29-37.
79. Qarshieva M. S. N. C. M., Shaptakov J. U. The Composition of the Income of Service Workers and Ways of its Improvement (On the Example of Educational Institutions) //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – Т. 4.

80. Nodirovna M. S. FOREIGN TO THE SECTORS OF ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN ATTRACTING INVESTMENTS.

81. Artikov Z. S. FACTORS INFLUENCING THE INCREASE IN PROFIT AND PROFITABILITY OF BUSINESS STRUCTURES IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY //Economics and Innovative Technologies. – 2022. – T. 2022. – №. 2. – C. 1.